

Classical Free Particle Lagrangian Consistent with Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

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Classical mechanics introduces a function, $L(x,v,t)$, called a Lagrangian. such that the classical action: $\int_{(t_1,t_1)} L(x,v,t)dt$ is stationary on variations of path, i.e. $\delta \text{Action} = 0$. This in turn leads to the differential equation: $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial v} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = 0$ (if there are no constraints). The Lagrangian, however, is not a unique function in that different forms may satisfy the same differential equation.

In particular, the Lagrangian (relativistic) for a free particle is usually written as: $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((1)). Given that $v=\text{constant}$, one has the almost trivial result: $dv/dt=0$. In other word, $\delta \text{Action}=0$ yields no extra information for this Lagrangian because $v=dx/dt$ by definition and $v=\text{constant}$ a priori, so the differential equation is $d/dt v=0$.

In principle, however, the action is varied with respect to paths. Dt appears automatically, but a path should depend on x which is absent in ((1)). We thus suggest that there may be an issue using this Lagrangian form even though it gives the correct $dv/dt=0$. In particular, we argue that physical information about x is lost. We suggest that one may write the free particle action in a Lorentz invariant manner (something we have argued in previous notes), namely $A = -Et+px$ (which is also a Lorentz invariant). This holds under the constraint that $v=x/t$. This can be shown to satisfy dv/dt , but at the same time there is a variation which satisfies $\delta \text{Action}=0$, namely: v is held constant, $ct \rightarrow ct+b$ and $x \rightarrow x+b$, where b is any arbitrary value. This implies uncertainty in both x and t beyond the usual solution $x=vt$. In other words, $x=vt$ is not the whole picture even in classical action theory.

Given that b may be any arbitrary value, this uncertainty in x and t , does not directly lead to free particle quantum mechanics. In fact, an arbitrary b is a problem. To obtain quantum mechanics, one needs to consider the notion of conservation of momentum which is inherent in both Newtonian mechanics and classical Lagrangian theory. In particular, if one has two particles with momentum p_1, p_2 (one dimension and nonrelativistically) and the same rest mass, m_0 , we show that Lagrangian theory predicts conservation of momentum for internal forces (no external forces present).. Thus, for a free particle, momentum conservation must be respected from classical considerations. Given an arbitrary b , a probability linked with this uncertainty in x would not conserve probability unless one fixes $b=\hbar/p$, i.e. makes it dependent on p in order to create orthogonality. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, i.e. free particle quantum mechanics.

Classical Lagrangian Theory

Classical Lagrangian theory, relativistic or not, is based on:

$$\Delta \text{Action} = \delta \int_{(t_1,t_2)} L(x,v,t) dt = 0 \quad ((2))$$

Here one tries to find a path $x(t)$ which makes the Action stationary. This leads formally to the differential equation:

$d/dt \partial L/\partial v - \partial L/\partial x = 0$ ((3)) (for no constraints) and $p = dL/dv$

$L(x,v,t)$, however, is not necessarily a unique function. Different forms may satisfy the same ((3)). For a relativistic free particle, the Lagrangian is usually written as:

$$L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv} \quad \text{for } c=1 \quad ((4))$$

For $v=\text{constant}$, $dL/dt = 0$, but this means that ((4)) and ((3)) really give no new information. One starts with $v=\text{constant}$ and so does not need Lagrangian theory to write: $dv/dt=0$

The nonrelativistic form from ((4)) is: $L = -m_0 + .5mvv$ ((5)) which is in keeping with the usual recipe: $L = \text{kinetic energy} - \text{potential}$.

We, however, suggest that ((4)) may not demonstrate the full information of $\delta \text{Action} = 0$ even in a classical scenario for the reason that $L(v)$ ((4)), whereas one would expect $L(x,v)$ at minimum because t enters through dt .

Special Relativistic Form of a Free Particle Lagrangian

We have proposed the alternative Lagrangian form: $\text{Action} = -Et + px$ ((5)) where:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad \text{and} \quad p = mv / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad (6)$$

many times before.

This action is Lorentz invariant (i.e. A is a Lorentz invariant), but also explicitly contains x, t and v . It holds with the constraint: $x/t=v$. One may obtain the Lagrangian: $L = -E(v) + p(v)v$ which satisfies $dL/dt=0$ because $dv/dt=0$, but again this yields no extra information about the problem. One already knows a priori that $v=\text{constant}$.

We argue, however, that the principle: $\delta \text{Action}=0$, even for a free particle reveals important information about paths because if one uses:

$$X \rightarrow x+b \quad \text{and} \quad ct \rightarrow ct+b, \quad \text{where } b \text{ is an arbitrary amount, } \delta A = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Thus, holding v constant, but moving to a different x and t (from the set $x=vt$) still satisfies $\delta A = 0$. We argue that this is the key information revealed by $\delta \text{Action} = 0$. This suggests that one does not only have the deterministic $x=vt$ (which does not require Lagrangian theory to obtain $x=vt$, only $v=\text{constant}$ and the definition dx/dt), but also uncertainty in x and t compatible with $\delta \text{Action} = 0$. Nevertheless, $\delta \text{Action} = 0$ yields the result that:

There is uncertainty in x and t for a free particle ((8))

At present, this uncertainty is b , which is an arbitrary amount and so there are no quantitative predictions. Any b value is as good as another and this is an issue.

Conservation of Momentum

Conservation of momentum is a principle found in Newtonian mechanics and also in the free particle Lagrangian theory as may be seen as follows. Relativistically, one has:

$$A_1 = -E_1 t + p_1 x \quad \text{and} \quad A_2 = -E_2 t + p_2 x \quad \text{or} \quad A = A_1 + A_2 = \text{Lorentz invariant} = (-E_1 - E_2) t + (p_1 + p_2) x \quad ((9))$$

Now $A = Lt$ for a free particle, so $L = -E_1 - E_2 + (p_1 + p_2)v$
Using $dL/dt=0$ one has $d/dt (E_1 + E_2) = 0$ for energy conservation and:

$d/dt \{(p_1 + p_2) v\} = 0$ Now $v = \text{constant}$, i.e. it is a parameter which describes the speed of the moving frame. Thus:

$$d/dt (p_1 + p_2) = 0 \quad ((10)) \quad \text{so momentum is conserved.}$$

In other words, classical free particle Lagrangian theory contains conservation of momentum. This concept must be preserved by the arbitrary b uncertainty in x and t . The question then becomes: How is this accomplished?

Uncertainty in x and t implies probability in both of these variables. Given a two body collision, one may consider the uncertainty in x only to see its relation with conservation of momentum. If b is an arbitrary value, then there is no link with momentum and hence its conservation. We thus suggest that b must be linked to momentum. This means that $b(p)$ or that the uncertainty in x depends on p and in t , on E .

Given an x_1 , one has an uncertainty $b(p)$. The question is: What is the uncertainty at x_2 ? Given translational invariance, one would suggest: $b(p)$ again. Thus, this implies regular uncertainty intervals of size $b(p)$, instead of a somewhat random function b of p . This leads to:

$$\exp(i b(p) x) \quad ((11))$$

As a candidate for the probability intervals. It is in keeping with translational invariance because $\exp(i b(p)x) \exp(-i b(p)x) = 1$.

In order to have conservation of momentum, the simplest solution is: $\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the traditional application of Lagrangian theory, or namely the principle $\delta \text{Action} = 0$ yields no new information for the free particle case for which v is defined as dx/dt and known to be a constant. Thus $d/dt dv/dt = 0$ is the differential equation needed and one does not need: $d/dt dL/dv \text{ partial} - dL/dx \text{ partial} = 0$. Thus, $x=vt$ does not need

to be derived from Lagrangian theory, but we suggest that there may be more information in $\delta A = 0$, than what is usually considered.

In particular, traditionally one uses: $L = -m_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$. This expression contains no x values, but one is supposed to vary a path in $\delta A = 0$ and so we suggest using an L which contains x , namely the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$ with the constraint $x/t = v$. If one writes: $L = -E + pv$, one again has no extra information for a free particle. The $A = -Et + px$ has a second solution for $\delta A = 0$, namely, v is held constant and $x \rightarrow x + b$ and $ct \rightarrow ct + b$. At this point, b is completely arbitrary. Thus, one sees that there is uncertainty in x and t , but has no idea what this uncertainty is. We then use arguments linked to conservation of momentum to show that the uncertainty in x should be proportional to \hbar/p and in t , to \hbar/E . This leads to conservation of p for two body scattering, i.e. a case for which there is no external force (only internal ones). Thus, the x and t uncertainties are p and E dependent for conservation reasons, we suggest. This in turn leads to the probability forms $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ which represent free particle quantum mechanics.